

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. Colonnade Square R16 A Locus Number (1a) (1b) (1c) → CHANGED TO (3) - (3c)

Progress of Excavation ^{16/I/80} After (2) cleared from ("known") N Balk R16 up → CHANGED BACK (1b) - (2) see Reverse

slope to N, shown in pre-existing edge of disturbance 65 cm. N of N R16 Balk that (1a) over (1b) over (2) - here a darker grey band phasing out under which a lighter greyish-buff deposit w/ many limestone

blocks. 17/I/80 (1a) "dry crust" taken out. R16A photoed with (1b) (2) (2a) (3b) (3) labelled. What is labelled (2a) in photo cleared as (2) in R16 and on 16/I/80 // 17/I/80, 10:15 - Took off few cms of (1b)

and true nature of stratification apparent (1b) Actually passes under both (2) (2a) which lenses out at edge of previous disturbance of all loci. It was only →

Locus Description (1a) DRY LIGHT GREY GRAVELY SAND (CRUST)

(1b) DRY LIGHT TAN GRAVELY SAND

(1c) Dark Dirt-Sand mix

Location in Square ^(1a) From disturbed cut-edge half way from R16 N Balk to S.T. N wall w/ interruption toward middle trench ((1b) shows through)

(1b) SAME, UNDER (1a) across trench from disturbance edge to N wall.

(1c) Small Patch upper NE corner beside S.T. wall

Under Locus _____ Over Locus _____ →

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials (1a) and (1b) have ^{small} stone frags.

(1a) which, as a dry crust passed over end of (2)-(2a) phasing out and terminating at edge of disturbance. (1b) - very clean sand phases into (i.e. 15) (3) as seen on remount of (2)-(2a) at patch of (3) showing in plan at E Balk ≈ 80 from R16 N Balk line. "(1b)" therefore really (3) or gravelly part (which interfaces w (3) as part of same stratum, could be designated (3a). (3)-(3c) (formerly (1b)) seems ancient at off-cult assessment and may prove similar to clean sand w/ concentrated limestone chips in N578 RS, etc. A disturbance of, tentatively O.K. harder packed rubble w/ tan clay etc. (1b) Then given new locus designation as (3)-(3c) (see photos). Basket of (1b)-(3) saved in basket. Next step: removal of slight remains of (2)-(2a) at edge of disturbance 65 cm from R16 N Balk.

In taking out what was thought to be termination of (2)-(2a) characteristic (2) - slightly grey sand with limestone chips continues sloping up under what was called at beginning of day (1b), then called (3)-(3c) (see above). Actually much simpler: (2a) ((2) in R16) covers (3) clean sand (no (3c) - no evidence ancient nor to be identified with clean sand-concentrated limestone chips in N578 RS). (2a) ((2) R16) overlaid against (3) sand (3) only shows at E Balk starting at N end against wall. (separated along wall by band of darker sand running against wall). Trouble is (2a) ((2) R16) comes up much like (3) - only slightly darker and given away by presence of small limestone chips - not concentrated or packed, but sprinkled throughout. We are having some wind and intermittent rains (both of today's down pours came at 2 times respectively that I had changed in mind about stratification and locus identification. See LOCUS SHEET (2)-(2a)